

Resistance in Chengte 232 to the two isolates tested is conditioned by a single gene that is allelic or closely linked to a gene in its progenitor, Toride 1. We conclude, therefore, that Chengte 232 inherited the gene from Toride 1.

Because Toride 1 carries *Pi-z'*, it is likely that *Pi-z'* controls the resistance in Chengte 232. The resistance genes of Tetep, however, were not transferred into Chengte 232. ■

Pest resistance—insects

Screening of rice hybrids for resistance to whitebacked planthopper, *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath)

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Twenty-four rice experimental hybrids were screened for whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) resistance at the adult plant stage under natural conditions at Bhupindra Rice Research Substation, Rauni (a hot spot of the insect at seedling stage), and under artificial conditions in a glasshouse at PAU. The field experiments were replicated three times using a

randomized complete block design. The glasshouse experiment was replicated twice using a completely randomized design.

Number of insects/10 hills in the field was counted by tapping plants. Damage was scored in the glasshouse experiment using the 0-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (see table).

PERH188, PERH207, PERH210, and PERH225 were found to be moderately resistant under both conditions and PERH239, PERH288, and PERH690 were considered to be susceptible.

Similar results were recorded for nearly half of the entries under both conditions. Differences, however, were noted in PERH125, PERH229,

Screening of rice hybrids under natural conditions at a hot spot in Rauni and under artificial infestation conditions, 1993 kharif.

Hybrid	Parentage	Insects/10 hills at Rauni (no.)	Damage score (0-9 scale)
PERH1	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1106-6-2	66	6.9
PERH2	Pb.CMS 8 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	55	7.2
PERH3	Pb.CMS 10 A/PAU1106-6-2	60	5.2
PERH7	Pb.CMS 1 A/PAU1106-6-2	44	6.6
PERH9	Pb.CMS 1 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	61	6.8
PERH38	Pb.CMS 2 A/PR106	25	5.7
PERH46	Pb.CMS 4 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	61	6.3
PERH125	Pb.CMS 8 A/IR13292-5-3	39	7.9
PERH134	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-1-1	145	5.8
PERH135	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	77	6.9
PERH188	Pb.CMS 10 A/PAU1106-5-4	39	4.5
PERH207	Pb.CMS 10 A/PR106	53	4.6
PERH210	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR32841-46-1-1	34	3.2
PERH225	Pb.CMS 2 A/IR32841-46-1-1	35	5.0
PERH229	Pb.CMS 2 A/PAU1106-21-4	191	4.1
PERH239	Pb.CMS 3 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	138	7.5
PERH244	Pb.CMS 3 A/PAU1106-21-4	165	3.6
PERH257	Pb.CMS 3 A/PR103	101	5.8
PERH288	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-29-1	193	8.1
PERH353	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR13292-5-3	34	6.7
PERH389	Pb.CMS 3 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	79	6.5
PERH588	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR31802-56-4	27	6.3
PERH577 A	Pb.CMS 2 A/IR31802-56-4	22	6.6
PERH690	Pb.CMS 58025 A/PAU1106-6-2	165	6.8
PR103 (check)	IR8/IR127-2-2	76	6.3
PR106 (check)	IR8//Peta*5/Belle Patna	83	8.4
PR108 (check)	Vijay/Ptb21	29	7.2
PR110 (check)	TN1/Patong 32//PR106	72	6.3

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PERH244, PERH353, PERH588, and PERH577 A. The differential behavior of the test entries suggests that rice germplasm should be screened for reaction to WBPH under both natural and artificial conditions. ■

Screening rice accessions for resistance to thrips

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Thrips, *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall), is a serious pest in rice nurseries in the tropical plains of Tamil Nadu. Both nymphs and adults can cause extensive damage to seedlings by feeding on the leaves, resulting in inward curling along the margins that can lead to scorching, wilting, and death.

In the first phase, we screened 122 accessions for reaction to thrips in the field during August 1992 and September 1993 at the Annamalai University Experimental Farm, Annamalaiagar. Each test entry was planted in moist soil in 0.7-m long rows, at a row space of 20 cm. Each entry was replicated three times, with one row per replication. Ptb33, the resistant check, and TN1, the

Reaction of rice accessions to thrips. Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

Accession	Field			Greenhouse		
	1992	1993	Reaction ^a	I	II	Reaction ^a
IR62	1	1	HR	1	1	HR
Ptb22	1	1	HR	1	1	HR
Ptb33	1	1	HR	1	1	HR
T235	1	1	HR	3	3.6	R
Afaamwanza 1-1-159	1	1	HR	7	7	S
Ptb19	3	3	R	3	3	R
Ptb20	3	3	R	3	3	R
Pokkall	3	3	R	3	3	R
CO 43	3	3	R	3.6	3.6	R
IET6012	3	3	R	3	3	R
IET6017	3	3	R	7	7	S
IET8833	3	3	R	3	3	R
IR49517-23-2-2-3-3	3.6	3.6	R	7	7	S
RP2271-433	3	3	R	7	7	S
IET9702	3	3	R	7	7	S
IET9709	3	3	R	7	7	S
IET9727	3	3	R	7.6	7.6	S
T117	3	3	R	7	7	S
T258	3	3	R	3.6	3.6	R
T401	3	3	R	7	7	S
T585	3.6	3.6	R	3	3	R

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, S = susceptible.

susceptible check, were sown randomly alongside the test entries and exposed to natural infestation. Damage was rated twice, at 14 d and 21 d after sowing, on a 0-9 scale where 0 = no damage; 1 =

rolling of terminal third of first leaf only; 3 = rolling of terminal third of first and second leaves; 5 = rolling of terminal half of first, second, and third leaves, yellowing of leaf tip; 7 = rolling of entire

length of all leaves, pronounced yellowing; and 9 = complete plant wilting, yellowing, and scorching. Five of the accessions were highly resistant and 16 resistant (see table).

In the second phase, the 21 resistant accessions were screened twice in the greenhouse. Entries were sown in 10-cm long rows in plastic trays (40 cm × 30 cm × 15 cm), filled 10-cm deep with soil. In each tray, 20 rows were sown in two strips. Ptb33 and TN1 were sown randomly with the test entries.

Each set of entries was replicated three times. Water was added regularly to maintain soil moisture. Leaves infested with *S. biformis* from the stock culture were collected and evenly distributed until the population reached 5 thrips/seedling. Seedlings were covered with a mylar film case with a muslin top. Damage was rated on the 0-9 scale 21 d after infestation. Three of the accessions were highly resistant, nine resistant, and the rest susceptible (see table). ■

Resistance to green leafhopper in rice varieties with different resistance genes

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While identifying sources of resistance to the Tamil Nadu populations of green leafhopper (GLH), *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant), we observed differences in levels of resistance among varieties identified as resistant to GLH at IRRI. Varieties with a known GLH resistance gene or resistance genes and varieties with an unidentified dominant GLH resistance gene were evaluated for damage rating in the seedbox screening test and for their effects on growth of Tamil Nadu GLH populations.

To study varietal reactions, Pankhari 203 with *Glh 1*; ASD7, Tendeng, Rhissa, Sefa, Badal 2, and Chota Digha with *Glh 2*; Chiknal with *Glh 3*; Ptb8 with

glh 4; ASD8 with *Glh 5*; Tapl796 with *Glh 6*; Moddai Karuppan with *Glh 7*; Choron Bawla with *Glh 1 + Glh 2*; Laki 659 with *Glh 3 + Glh 5*; and monogenic varieties Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, ARC10318,

and susceptible check TN1 were sown in 40-cm rows in wooden trays (60 × 45 × 10 cm) with five replications. At 7 d after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 15/row, infested with 5-6 second-instar nymphs/

Plant damage rating and population growth of green leafhopper on rice varieties with different genes for resistance^a. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Gene(s) for resistance	Damage rating ^b	Population growth (no.)
Pankhari 203	<i>Glh 1</i>	9.0 a	201.8 ab
ASD7	<i>Glh 2</i>	3.0 b	41.9 efg
Tendeng	<i>Glh 2</i>	2.2 bcd	56.4 d
Rhissa	<i>Glh 2</i>	1.4 de	54.8 d
Sefa	<i>Glh 2</i>	1.8 cde	47.0 def
Badal 2	<i>Glh 2</i>	1.0 e	31.2 ghi
Chota Digha	<i>Glh 2</i>	1.4 de	51.0 de
Chiknal	<i>Glh 3</i>	2.6 bc	50.0 de
Ptb8	<i>glh 4</i>	2.2 bcd	39.6 fg
ASD8	<i>Glh 5</i>	2.6 bc	47.4 def
Tapl796	<i>Glh 6</i>	1.0 e	23.0 i
Moddai Karuppan	<i>Glh 7</i>	1.0 e	12.4 j
Hashikalmi	One dominant	9.0 a	187.0 c
Ghaiya	One dominant	9.0 a	197.0 bc
ARC10313	One dominant	9.0 a	190.0 bc
Choron Bawla	<i>Glh 1 + Glh 2</i>	1.8 cde	38.8 fgh
Laki 659	<i>Glh 3 + Glh 5</i>	1.0 e	8.6 j
TN1	None	9.0 a	212.8 a

^aMean of five replications. In a column, means followed by the same letters are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT. ^bDamage scored using SES.